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SPECIFIC LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS FOR FOSTERING STUDENTS' SUSTAINABILITY MINDSET

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ABSTRACT

One of the core and fundamental principles of sustainable development is responsible consuming of natural resources in order to maintain and better to increase them for future generations. The implementation of this principle is not possible without formation of a special world outlook of each member of society - the mindset of responsibility for the expenditure of resources and conditions regulating the use of resources.

Transformation of modern society from industrial into knowledge-based society requires a substantial increase of the role of the universities because they are just those organizations where the knowledge is gathered and disseminated. Today it is more common for universities to focus their efforts on developing competences rather than mindsets of future engineers. Apart of other considerations, another important issue is proposed for discussion in this article: a need to form/change students' mindsets, a need to develop specific learning environments at HEIs.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability and Engineering Education

Keywords: Sustainability, specific learning environment, sustainability mindset, engineering education.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, global environmental challenges in conjunction with the issues of social responsibility are recognized as extremely important for all mankind. The search for ways to solve them has led to the development of the concept of sustainable

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development in the 1980s and then to the first steps towards its implementation. The meaning of the concept of sustainable development is to identify the prerequisites and conditions for harmonizing socio-economic and environmental development and the lifestyle of every person on our planet. According to this concept, people must satisfy their needs in such a way that fundamental measures of the biosphere processes established over the millions of years are not violated and life of the next generations is not jeopardized [1]. In general, it is assumed that sustainable development should be characterized by the economic efficiency, biosphere compatibility, social justice, and comprehensive security through the harmonious development of the personality, society and nation as well as through the well-considered interaction with the nature [2].

On September 25, 2015, the States Members of the United Nations adopted the Agenda for Sustainable Development until 2030. It contains a number of goals aimed at eradicating poverty, conserving resources of the planet, and ensuring well-being for all. Each of the 17 Goals contains a number of indicators to be achieved by 2030. To achieve the Goals in the field of sustainable development, shared efforts of the governments, private sector, and civil society are needed.

Education is recognized as the most important mechanism for ensuring sustainable social and economic and spiritual (intellectual) development. This statement is also emphasized in the materials of the World Summit on Sustainable Development (Johannesburg, 2002). The key role in achieving the goals of sustainable development has to be played by the education system, which is called "a decisive factor for changes" in many UN documents. The wide recognition of the education and closely related upbringing and enlightenment as a decisive factor has made it necessary not only to consider the main issues related to the ecology and social responsibility in the process of training of engineers, but also foster the sustainability mindset of the students.

1 SUSTAINABILITY MINDSET

Currently, the world community is paying even more attention to sustainable development of our society: moderate consumption, greening and environmentalization of professional activities, responsible resource management, and other aspects that affect nature and society as a whole, as well as the ability to conserve resources for future generations. Considering of sustainable development principles is an integral part of training specialists in the field of engineering and technology. Graduates should build their professional activities in accordance with ethical, social, environmental standards, be responsible for the technical decisions they make, be able to forecast and reduce/prevent damage from the technologies they develop. The modern educational process requires adjustments in order to introduce the principles of sustainable development into the training process of engineers.

One of the core and fundamental principles of sustainable development is responsible consuming of natural resources in order to maintain and better to increase them for future generations. The implementation of this principle is not possible without formation of a special world outlook of each member of society - the mindset of responsibility for the expenditure of resources and conditions regulating the use of resources. Essentially, it involves social responsibility of each member of our society and communities at large (companies, enterprises, public organizations and others). This personal and corporate responsibility includes social consequences of all their

activities and all kinds of their decisions concerning not only consuming exhaustible resources and resource saving, but also measures taken to create conditions necessary for this [3,4]. It is not a coincidence that that in the modern world exist and develop such trends as Responsible Research and Innovations, Responsible Industry, Technology Assessment, etc [5].

We can assume that an integrating condition for the realization of any of these trends is not only the formation of the competences of each person (specialist), participating in the decision-making process. It is important to manage development of sustainability mindset and social responsibility competence. These conditions cannot be met without active and decisive contribution of the education system at all stages. New models for sustainable education must be aimed at changing the mindsets of future generations beginning at an early age then fostered through formal education at undergraduate, graduate and professional levels.

To the credit of modern Russian engineering education, it is worth mentioning that training of socially responsible graduates became a notable trend. This ongoing trend is enhanced and supported by the requirements of Federal State Educational Standards, real academic activities within development and implementation of educational programs, curriculum requirements of several courses and disciplines, and, rarely, in scientific research. The process of developing competences among future graduates is realized along a study program and requires from students acquisition of fundamental knowledge and skills to be applied in practice. Usually it implies to provide ordinary and well-known conditions: qualified scientific and pedagogical staff, modern facilities, good connections with employers (cooperation with industry). To form any outlook in general, in addition to the above conditions, it is necessary to create a specific environment that forms the appropriate mindset of students.

2 SPECIFIC ENVIRONMENT AT UNIVERSITIES

Engineering influences directly the quality of life of the mankind; therefore, the actions of engineers require honesty, impartiality, justice, and efficiency. Their actions have to be aims at health protection, safety, and wellbeing of people. Fostering a socially-oriented mindset and behavior of future engineers requires from the educational organizations and educational process to implement adjustments in order to introduce the principles of sustainable development into the training process of engineers.

Analysis of the current state of implementation of the concept of sustainable development in the system of higher professional education shows that the most common approach is the introduction of a number of new disciplines in the field of sustainable development in the curriculum, particularly ecology, resourceefficiency management, etc. [6,7] However, those measures are not enough to develop a culture of sustainable development among the academic and management staff and students. This paper introduces a new holistic approach that aims to create a specific environment within a university for fostering sustainable development and social responsibility mindset that allows future engineers to take managerial, project, economic, social, and political decisions that are adequate to the crisis situations and trends faced in all spheres of life of the nation and the world community at large.

Despite the application of competence-based approach to the process of educational programs' development, the contents of the programs and teaching and learning methods used, as a rule, do not allow fostering future specialists' skills, attitudes and knowledge on a level needed for winning in a competitive battle. At this, it is necessary to mention that representatives of industry confirm a good level of basic knowledge

and theoretical background on certain disciplines. However, they point out as an evident drawback a low level of key competences' formation (professional skills and soft skills), as well as a low level of practical skills needed for solving real engineering tasks and problems.

Introduction of the competence-based approach to the designing of educational programs is a necessary, but not sufficient condition required for guarantee the expected level of future specialists' competences of social responsibility within the educational process. The pivotal factors ensuring the formation of required competences within the educational process are the teaching and learning methods and conditions for their implementation (including the potential and qualification of faculty) and the specific university environments that support fostering of competences.

The analysis of world's best practices in identifying and developing specific learning environments allowed to select most challenging and vital types of environments listed below:

1. Environment for sustainable development, including
 - a. Ecological (greening) environment
 - b. Social responsibility environment
 - c. Lean production environment
2. Creative environment
3. Entrepreneurial environment
4. Project based learning environment.

As mentioned above today it is more common for universities to focus their efforts on developing competences rather than mindsets of future engineers. Apart of other considerations a necessary condition to form/change students' mindsets is that higher education institutions need to develop specific learning environments, as shown in the Fig. 1 [8].

Fig. 1. Specific learning environment

Specific environments such as "ecological environment", "environment forming responsibility", "creative (innovative) environment", etc., create the basis for the

development of relevant competencies at university, both for students and teachers, and for managerial staff. Orientation of the university on purposeful formation of specific environments will allow in a more successful way and in a shorter period of time to implement qualified training of graduates in the field of engineering and technology that meet the requirements of the labor market and the modern society as a whole.

The paper presents an ongoing research at Tomsk Polytechnic University with the support of Association for Engineering Education of Russia. The key direction of the research is changing the paradigm of thinking and professional activity of the future engineer, fostering new students' mindset, aimed at understanding the responsibility for resource endowment of the next generations, changing consumption patterns, forming a new lifestyle. The priority is given to the development of tools for the implementation of (scientific, theoretical, informative, pedagogical, technological, organizational) aspects of sustainable development concept in the system of training students in the field of engineering and technology.

The main objective of the research is the development and pilot testing of methods, tools and actions for creating specific university environments that contribute to fostering sustainable development and social responsibility mindset.

We assume that creation of such university environment will allow to transform the mindset of all stakeholders involved in the educational process (students, academic staff and administration of the university). It will ensure more sustainable development of students' competences, facilitate their employability and will become one of the most important steps how the educational process could respond the big challenges.

The toolkit proposed for the development is universal in nature and can be applied in different types of universities (technical, classical, medical, etc.) in order to promote creation of specific environments of any type. The complex of actions for the development of specific environments can be adapted to the needs of the country, region and the university itself. The actions should be continuously pursued, thus contributing not only to the initial creation of the environment, but also to its maintenance and development.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Revealing the new paradigm of education in the interests of sustainable development, it is necessary to point out the main aspect of the orientation of any moral teaching. It involves formation of a new mindset. In the available nowadays research studies this issue is not highlighted enough when talking about training of future engineers. Nevertheless, in our opinion, mindset development is an essential and fundamental element in the structure of professional engineering activity. Despite the recognition of the importance of reforming education systems for ensuring sustainable development, the efforts are not successful enough. This is partly due to the fact that pedagogical traditions are based on the transfer of existing knowledge, the reproduction of real connections and attitudes reflected in the public consciousness. The future is always more or less uncertain. This fact determines, in essence, the establishment of fundamentally new pedagogical and management tasks related to the formation of a sustainable development mindset.

The necessary fundamental basis needed by every graduate for systemic and holistic solving of real-life problems is fostered through the prism of professional competency. A universal, creative, developing personality of a future professional can be formed

only if there is a continuous pedagogical process and each stage of it is based on integrated principles and methods and has a core aim – professional competency of an engineer, who will be able to ensure sustainable development.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987. Our Common Future. Oxford University Press, Oxford (1987)
- [2] The World Bank Report. (2001) Constructing Knowledge Societies: New Challenges for Tertiary Education. Washington, DC: The World Bank
- [3] Domínguez Pachón M.J. (2009) Responsabilidad Social Universitaria. Humanismo y Trabajo Social Vol 8, pp. 37-67
- [4] Lina Gomez (2014), The Importance of University Social Responsibility in Hispanic America: A Responsible Trend in Developing Countries, in Gabriel Eweje (ed.) Corporate Social Responsibility and Sustainability: Emerging Trends in Developing Economies (Critical Studies on Corporate Responsibility, Governance and Sustainability, Volume 8) Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp.241 – 268.
- [5] Grunwald, A., Wyss, M., Peppoloni, S. (2015) The imperative of sustainable development: elements of an ethics of using geo-resources responsibly. Geoethics. Ethical challenges and case studies in earth sciences, pp. 26-35.
- [6] Huntzinger, D.N., Hutchins, M.J., Gierke, J.S., Sutherland, J.W., (2007) Enabling sustainable thinking in undergraduate engineering education. International Journal of Engineering Education, 23(2), pp. 218-230.
- [7] Koester RJ, Eflin J, Vann J. (2006) Greening of the campus: a whole-systems approach. J. Clean. Product. 14, pp. 769-779
- [8] Yu. Pokholkov, K. Tolkacheva, M. Chervach (2017), Concept of responsible education - new trend in the higher education area, Proceedings of INTED2017 Conference, Valencia, 6-8 March, 2017